

ALGORITHM AND PROGRAM FOR DETECTION OF UNAUTHORIZED ACCESS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK BASE

Tursunmurodov Aslbek Nurvali o'g'li

Master's degree, Faculty of Cyber-Security,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan

Abstract: Recently, intrusion detection systems (IDS) have been introduced to effectively secure networks. Using neural networks and machine learning in detecting and classifying intrusions are powerful alternative solutions. In this research paper, both of Gradient descent with momentum (GDM)-based back-propagation (BP) and Gradient descent with momentum and adaptive gain (GDM/AG)-based BP algorithms are utilized for training neural networks to operate like IDS. To investigate the efficiency of the two proposed learning schemes, a neural network based IDS is built using the proposed learning algorithms. The efficiency of both algorithms is inspected in terms of convergence speed to achieve system learning, and elapsed learning time using various settings of neural network parameters. The result demonstrated that the GDM/AG-based BP learning algorithm outperforms the GDM-based BP learning algorithm.

Keywords: Intrusion detection systems (IDSs), Neural networks (NNs), Back-propagation (BP).

Introduction. The recent improvements in computer networks techniques in addition to the Internet wide popularity increase the importance of digital communications in all life activities. At the same time, the effect of hackers (intruders) on networks performance increases. They may have unauthorized network access by which they can alter; manipulate exchanged information or denial the network services via increasing network traffic. Therefore, securing networks against different types of attacks becomes a major research problem for many scholars. As a

result, many traditional security techniques have been introduced in the past such as antivirus, spyware & authentication mechanism. Such traditional systems are not sufficient to fully protect computer systems and networks against threats. Intrusion Detection & Prevention systems are introduced as alternative powerful security techniques. An intrusion detection could be defined as the process of analyzing system and network activities looking for nasty and unauthorized ones. The main aim of IDS is to find and catch the perpetrators before they perform any real damage to the systems, and networks. Recently, IDSs became a major part of any information assurance system. The functionality of IDSs is considered as a complement to the functionality of firewalls. That is, the functionality of firewalls is to protect digital information exchanging and prohibit intrusions while the functionality of IDS is to detect whether the network is under attack or not. IDSs are also used to detect whether the security imposed firewall security is penetrated or not. Hence, a good security system should have both of firewall and IDS to improve network security. Despite the prevention techniques, a good and reliable intrusion system should be available to prevent our systems from being attacked by criminals, and cyber-attacks. Such intrusion detection system should defend integrity, confidentiality, and all other security metrics. The well-known IDSs design approaches include but not limited to data mining approach, statistical approach, machine learning approach, expert system approach, pattern recognition approach and neural networks approach. These approaches represent the standards in developing IDS. This paper proposes two neural networks learning algorithms to train the neural networks for acting as IDS. These algorithms are the GDM-based BP and the GDM/AGbased BP learning techniques. The performance of both algorithms is investigated in terms of convergence speed to achieve system learning, and elapsed learning time using various settings of neural network parameters. The results demonstrated that GDM/AGbased BP learning scheme surpasses GDM-based BP learning scheme with respect to convergence speed and CPU time required to achieve system learning.

Materials. The main goal of IDS is the protect network, and computer resource's and their information from internal misuse, and external attacks. Data must

be immediately analyzed upon arrival. Such analysis should be done quickly. In discovery, the IDS must timely alert system admin to prevent further damage in the system resources and/or information. IDSs should not cause any substantial overhead and/or bottlenecks in the system or network resources

Methods. In contrast to the misuse based IDSs, anomaly based IDSs are motivated by their ability to detect new (unknown to the system) attacks, their independence from the operating system specific information, and their training simplicity as it trained a rule/policy only which are utilized in detecting unauthorized users or network packets. The anomaly based IDSs suffer from generating high rate of false alarms which is considered as one of their main disadvantages. This problem has a negative impact on network key performance metrics such as latency time, throughput, and packet losses rate. It also participates in increasing the network admin management efforts.

Results. The problem of high rate of false alarms arises when IDS uses limited network information which may occur as a result of changing normal network behaviors without correspondingly updating IDS [4]. Also, the system or user normal behavior may change over time, causing the IDS to be not available for some period of time. The intruder may attack the system in that period of time. One more dangerous drawback for the anomaly based IDSs is that during the user or system normal behavior learning phase the system may be attacked. To simplify the evaluation process of IDSs, a number of characteristics for a good IDS has been presented. These characteristics can be summarized as follows:

1. Accuracy The IDS is accurate if it does not issue any false alerts by considering nonintrusive activities as intrusive.
2. Continuity The IDS should work continuously without any human interaction or supervision.
3. Reliability The IDS should be reliable to be able to work in the background of the observed system, and its functions should be observable form the system's foreground.

4. Fault Tolerance If the system is corrupted, the IDS should be able to survive and restore its knowledge-base during the restart time.

5. Self-Monitoring By monitoring itself, the IDS ensures that it has not been wrecked and also, it detects any deviations from normal behavior.

6. Minimal Overhead The system’s overhead introduced by the IDS should be minimal and it should not slow the system.

7. Timeliness The IDS should be able to react analyze and alerts the system’s admin as soon as possible to give him/her time to react before the attack is conducted.

8. Integrity Systems are different from the usage point of view that is each system has his own usage pattern, and the IDS should be easily adaptable to these patterns.

9. Dynamicity The IDS should be automatically able to deal with system’s behavior changes (profile changes as a result of adding and removing applications) overtime.

10. Performance The IDS performance depends mainly on its information processing rate. This information processing rate should be very high (fast) otherwise the IDS is likely to be not possible.

11. Completeness The IDS should be able to detect all types of attack which is known as system’s completeness.

Conclusion: This research paper studies the performance of the GDM-based BP and the GDM/AGbased BP algorithms in learning neural network act as intrusion detection system for detecting spoofed IP’s attacks. Using various system parameter setting, a performance comparison is conducted between the two studied algorithms in terms of convergence speed and CPU time required to achieve system learning. The results demonstrated that the GDM/AG-based BP learning algorithm outperforms the GDM-based BP learning algorithm. Based on the results obtained in this study, it is recommended to use the GDM/AGbased BP as a learning engine in designing neural networks intrusion detection systems.

References:

1. Dass, M., Cannady, J., & Potter, W. D. (2003). Learning intrusion detection system. In The 16th international flairs conference (pp. 12–16), St. Augustine, Florida, May 12–14, 2019.
2. Cannady, J. (1998). Artificial neural networks for misuse detection. In National information systems security conference.
3. Valdes, A., & Anderson, D. (2020). Statistical methods for computer usage anomaly detection using NIDES. SRI International: Technical report.
4. Elfeshawy, N. A., & Faragallah, Osama S. (2018). Divided two-part adaptive intrusion detection system. *Wireless Networks*, 19, 301–321.
5. Zhang, Z., Li, J., Manikopoulos, C., Jorgenson, J., & Ucles, J. (2001). A hierarchical anomaly network intrusion detection system using neural network classification. In WSES International conference on: Neural networks and applications (NNA 01), February 2021.